

RAKTAMOKSHAN: A KEY THERAPEUTIC APPROACH FOR TWAKAVIKAR

Dr. Swapnil Sampatrao Garje^{1*}, Dr. Balasaheb Kacheshwar Jundhare²¹Associate Professor, Panchakarma Department, Matoshri Ayurved College, Hospital and Research Centre, Karjule Harya, Dist – Ahilyanagar, MAaharashtra.²Associate Professor, Kayachikitsa, Rashtrasant Janardhan Swami Ayurved College and Research Centre, At. Post – Kokamthan, Taluka – Kopargaon, Dist- Ahilyanagar, MAaharashtra.**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Swapnil Sampatrao Garje^{1*}, Dr. Balasaheb Kacheshwar Jundhare² (2026). Raktamokshan: A Key Therapeutic Approach For Twakavikar. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(2), 231–235. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/01/2026

Article Revised on 25/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Nowadays *Tvachavikar* is most common skin disease, and it has social impact. It is a skin problem mentioned in Ayurvedic literature with *Kapha* and *Pitta* morbidly or pathology. In classical different text of Ayurveda and Acharyas emphasize the *Shodhana* therapy as the line of treatment at various places. In *Shodhana* treatment *Raktamokshan* is highlight specially because in *Samprapti Ghataka Rakta* is mainly involved as *Dushya*. In the present topic, *Raktamokshana* Acharya Sushruta propounds practical guidelines for bloodletting and claims it as most effective therapy in half of the body ailments. In all different methods for bloodletting such as *Jalaukavacharana Karma*, *Prachhanna Karma* and *Siravedhana Karma*, *Jalaukaavacharna Karma* (leech therapy) is considered as the ideal method to expel out the vitiated blood safely, quickly, and effectively. The vitiated external environment undoubtedly affects the body's internal ailments. Large community prevalence studies have demonstrated that about 20-30% of the world population have various skin problems requiring attention. So *Raktamokshan* is one of the important *Panchkarma* treatments to cure various type of *Tvacha vikar* highlighting in this topic.

KEYWORDS: Raktamokashna, *Tvachavikar*, *Jalaukavacharana Siravedhana* Vata, Pitta, Kapha, Dosha.**INTRODUCTION**

Tvacha is derived from “*Tvach Samavarne*” *dhatu* meaning the covering of the body. There are 7 layers of skin named from superficial to deep as *Avabhasini*, *Lohita*, *Sveta*, *Tamra*, *Vedini*, *Rohini* and *Mamsadhara*.^[1] The disease affect on these layers which are *Avabhasini sidhmam* and *Padma kantakam*, in *Lohita tilakalakam*, *Nyaccam* and *Vyangam*, in *Sveta charmadalam*, *Masakam* and *Ajagallikam*, in *Tamra kilasam* and also *Kusta* in *Vedini kusta* and *Visarpa* in *Rohini Granthi*, *Arbudam*, *Apache*, *Slipadam* and *Galagandam*, in *Mamasadhara bhagandharam*, *Vidradi* and *Arsas*.^[2] Any disease that involves skin hampers many functions and gives the person a hideous look. As skin diseases are perceptible to others, they are more painful for the patient and troublesome for the physician. Several skin diseases affect the person's psychological status and disturb the social life, thus patient have some kind of inferiority complex The texts of Ayurveda consider

Rakta Dusti as one of the prime causes of skin diseases. On the other hand, patients may get relief after letting out the vitiated *Rakta*. Acharya Sushruta said practical guidelines for bloodletting and claims it as most effective therapy in half of the body ailments. Among various methods for bloodletting such as *Jalaukavacharana Karma*, *Prachhanna Karma* and *Siravedhana Karma*, *Jalaukaavacharna Karma* (leech therapy) is considered as the ideal method to expel out the vitiated blood safely, quickly, and effectively. *Tvacha* is the largest organ of the body and constitutes 16% of the body weight. Nowadays drastic changes have occurred due to global warming, unfavorable food regimes, stress, unpredictable weather transitions etc. The vitiated external environment undoubtedly affects the body's internal ailments. Large community prevalence studies have demonstrated that about 20-30% of the world population have various skin problems requiring attention.^[6]

RAKTAMOKSHAN**Classification of Raktamokshana**

There are two types of Raktamokshan i.e.

1. *Anushastra visravan* includes *Shringavcharan*, *Jalaukavacharan*, *Alabu* and *Gati*.
2. *Shastravisravan* includes *Prachhan* and *Shiravedha*.

Precise time for Raktamokshana: This procedure should not do in very cold season, not in very hot season, not after excessive *Swedan* and not in very warm condition.

Importance of Raktamokshan: Time to time perform Raktamokshan does not produce *Tvagadoshas* (skin disorders), *Granthirogas* (cystic disorders), *Shopha* (oedema or swelling) and *Shonitajanyarogas* (blood born or blood related disorders).

Raktamokshana procedure: This whole method is categorized in three parts

- i. *Purva Karma* (Pre-procedure)
- ii. *Pradhana Karma* (Main Procedure)
- iii. *Paschat Karma* (Post-procedure)

Purva Karma (Pre procedure): *Yavagu* or liquid diet are given before doing procedure which are opposite in qualities of the aggravated *Dosha*. *Purvakarma* is indicated for liquefaction of *Doshas* and make them mobile into blood and removing vitiated blood containing that liquefied *Dosha* so it is very necessary to do internal and external *Snehan* and *Swedana karma*.

1) Shringavacharana^[7]

Indication- *Shringa* is *Ushna*, *Madhur* and *Snigdha* in nature therefore it is used to treat *Vatic* disorders.

Principal and procedure- In this procedure, sucking of vitiated *Rakta* through mouth by using the cow's horn. *Shringa* entering area should be 3 *Angula* and length should be 18 *Angula*.

2) Alabu^[8]

Principal and procedure- Extracting blood through the creating vacuum with the help of heat source using bottle guard or *Alabu*.

Indication- It has property of *Katu*, *Ruksh* and *Tikshana* so it is used in *Kapha* disorders. It should be 12 *Angula* in length and 18 *Angula* in diameter.

3) Ghati- Same as *Alabu* in length and diameter. It is used in decreasing *Gulma* shape and size.

4) Jalaukavacharan:^[9] Leeches are residence inside water and also developed from water. They are *Madhur* in *Rasa*. So, it is used in *Rakta* vitiated with *Pitta*. There are 12 types of leeches. Six are *Savisha* and six are *Nirvisha*.

Savisha jalauka: *Krishna*, *Karbura*, *Algarda*, *Indrayudha*, *Samudrika* and *Gochandana*. *Nirvisha* jalauka: *Kapila*, *Pingala*, *Sankumukhi*, *Mushika*, *Pundarika* and *Saavarika*.

Indication: Leeches are used in *Grathita* & *Avagadharakta*, in *Bala*, *Vridhdha*, *Bhiru*, *Stri*, *Durbala*, *Raja* and *Paramsukumar*.

Main procedure of application of leeches: After *Snehan* and *Swedan*, patient should be made to sit or lie down. In non-lesion area, a lesion is formed by sharp instrument because non lesion part of affected area is neither attached nor sucked by leeches.

Covering- During suction process, cover them except at their mouth with thin cotton cloth or swab soaked with the cold water.

Removal of leeches- A pinch of turmeric powder or *Saindhav* salt is used at its suction end for the removal of leeches.

Post leech application: After the removal of the leech, *Shatdhautgrita* or *Madhu* should be applied over wound (formed by leeches) or do bandage of that area.

4) Pracchanakarma^[10]

Principle & procedure - first, a tourniquet is tied slightly above the affected area and then, with the help of sharp instrument multiple, straight, neither very deep nor superficial, even not very close to other incisions are made to avoid damage of vital structures (*Marma*, *Shira*, *Snayu*, *Sandhi* etc).

After procedure apply the medicated powder over the *Pracchana* site.

5) Siravyadhanakarma^[11]

Precise time for Siravedhana: Best time for *Siravedhana* is in rainy season but in clear sky, in summer season but in cool time and in *Hemant ritu* but in the noon.

Shan anusar use of sharp and blunt instrument in Siravyadhan: In *Mansal Pradesh* use *Yavamatra shastra*, in other than *Mansal Pradesh* use *Yavamatra brihimukha yantra* or half of *Yavamatra brihimukha yantra* and on the *Asthi* use half *Yava matra* with *Kutharika shastra*.

Siravyadhan procedure: After *Purvakarma* and at suitable time, patient should sit or in standing posture and tie a tourniquet neither very tight nor very loose above the *Sira*. Now, use suitable *Shastra* for suitable site and do *Siravedhan karma*.

Rakta nirharan praman: 1 *Prastha*.

Samyak Srava Lakshana- First, vitiated blood comes from *Vedhan* site. After that non-vitiated blood come and stop itself after certain time. Lightness in the body, pain subsides, decrease spreading rate of disease and feels happiness.

Indication of Raktamokshana in Tvachavikar

1. *Kushtha* (Obstinate skin diseases)

2. *Vipsara* (Infective disease of the skin)
3. *Pidaka* (Skin Eruption)
4. *Raktapitta* (Bleeding Disorders)
5. *Vyanga* (Pigmentation of Face)
6. *Tilakalaka* (Moles)
7. *Dadru* (Fungal infection of Dermis)
8. *Shitra* (Lucoderma)
9. *Pama* (Scabies)
10. *Asramandala* (Reddish patches on the skin)
11. *Kandu* (Itching), *Mashaka* (A type of mole)
12. *Raktatwaka* (Redness of the skin)
13. *Charamadala* (A Form of skin disease characterized by abnormal thickening of the Dermis)

Contraindication of *Raktamokshana* in *Tvachavikar*

1. *Sarvang shopha* (anasarca)
2. *Kshina* (emaciation)
3. *Amlabhojana Nimitta Pandu* (Anemia due to intake of sour food)
4. *Arsha* (hemorrhoids)
5. *Udara* (ascites)
6. *Garbhini* (pregnancy).

Methods of checking blood after *Raktamokshana*

There are four procedures to stop the bleeding

(i) **Sandhan:** The drugs like *Lodhra* and *Udumbar* having astringent properties are possessed to bring an adhesion of the wound.

(ii) **Skandan:** Cooling measure such as application of ice, cold water etc. tends to thicken the localised blood.

(iii) **Pachan:** Alkalis and Alkaline preparations produce suppuration in such a wound called as *Pachana*.

(iv) **Dahan:** Checking the blood by property of contracting the *Sira*.

Sequence of blood checking remedy

Skandan, Sandhan, Pachan- These three procedures should be used first sequentially.

Daha- If bleeding does not stopped by above three procedures then lastly should do *Daha*.

Challenges facing during *Raktamokshan*^[12]

- (i) *Asrav* (no oozing of blood)
- (ii) *Alpa Srava* (less amount of blood flow)
- (iii) *Ati Rakta Srava* (more amount of blood flow)

Cause of *Asrav* of *Rakta* during *Raktamokshana*: A person suffering from loss of consciousness, fatigued or exhausted, suppression of the flatus, faeces and urine, overcome with sleep and coward.

Characteristic feature of *Asrav* and *Alpa srav*: Itching, swelling, redness, burning, suppuration and pain in the part to which it is confined.

Medication of *Asrav* and *Alpa srava* of *Rakta* during *Raktamokshan* procedure: *Gharshan* (rubbing)- By application of *Lavan* and *Madhu* mixed with powder of three to four drugs or all drugs over procedure site. Drugs- *Ela, Karpur, Kustha, Tagar, Patha, Devdaru,*

Vidanga, Chitraka, Trikatu, Grihadhum, Haridra and *Karanjphala*.

Cause of *Atisrava* of blood: Excessive heat environment, excess *Swedan*, injudiciously deep incision and by unexperienced surgeon.

Characteristic feature of *Atisrava*: *Shirobhitaap, Adhimanth, Timir, Dhatukshaya, Akshepaka, Pakshaghata, Ekangvikara, Trishna, Daha, Hikka, Kasa, Swas, Pandu* and death.

Treatment of excessive loss of blood during *Raktamokshan*

1. *Avapidan- Lodhra, Madhuka, Gairika, Sankha* and *Sukti* powders
2. *Avachurnana- Saal, Sarja, Arjuna*, ash of silk cloth etc powders
3. *Garshana- Samudraphena* and *Laksha* powder
4. *Bandhan*- Tight bandaging.
5. *Parisheka*- sprinkling of cold and medicated liquids.

Use of *Shashtra* and *Anushastra karma*, if medication fail to check bleeding

1. *Daha karma* by *Kshar* and *Agni*
2. *Siravedhan* of branching of same *Sira* and
3. Lastly approaches according to complications.

Post *Raktamokshana* measures- After loss of *Rakta* during *Raktamokshan*, there is possible increase of *Vata dosha* and decrease of *Agni* take place. So, maintain the *Vata* and *Agni* of patient by these measures

1. *Agnivardhaka Aahar*- use *Natisheet, Amlarahita, Laghu* and *Snigdha Aahar*
2. *Raktavardhaka Aahar*
3. *Sheet seka* and slight warm *Ghrita parisheka* should do if *Shopha* and pain takes place after *Raktamokshan*
4. *Shita annapaan*- use *Kakolyadi kwath* mixed with *Shita*
5. *Raktapaan*- use animals blood like *Varaah, Maahish, Hiran* etc
6. *Snigdha Aahar*- use *Ksheer* and *Yusha*.

Benefits of *Raktamokshana* in *Tvachavikar*

Raktamokshana is a unique way to get rid of skin disease. Skin diseases are manifestation of contaminated blood tissues. Skin is an important parameter to interpret one's health status, such as dehydration, febrile state, allergic manifestation and infection the diseases that are not cured by dry, cold, hot therapies should be better treated with *Raktamokshana*. *Rakta* is contaminated with vitiated *Vatta, Pitta, Kapha* respectively, and manifest into various type of *Tvachavikar* like *Kushta, Mahakushta, Shudrarog*, etc. When all *Shaman, Shodhan (Virechan)* treatment fails, *Raktaokshan* shows fantastic results. It's also perform in *Anupdesha, Pittaj prakruti* despite of disease free conditions in order to prevent skin diseases.^[13]

Skin diseases are more prevalent in *Anupdesha* as compared to other *Desha*. *Raktamokshana* discards the contaminated *Rakta* with the help of *Siravedha*, *Jalaukavacharn* in case of generalised *Raktaj Dushti*. Small incision at unhealing wound proved best in healing process considering *Vattaj*, *Pittaj* and *Kahaj* contamination of.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Rakthamokshana is pondering as *Ardha chikitsa* and due to *Ashraya ashrayi bhava*, it acts on *Pitta dosha* too. By *Rakthamokshana*, *Srotasa Shodhana* is to reach, which further helps in abatement of *Tvachavikar*. *Raktamokashan* is the perfect dealer for many skin diseases. According to Ayurveda, *Tvacha* is formed at the time of gestation. According to *Acharya Sushruta* there are seven layers of skin, named as *Avabhasini*, *Lohita*, *Shweta*, *Tamra*, *Vedini*, *Rohini*, *Mamsadhara* whereas *Acharya Charaka* said them as *Udakdhara*, *Asrukdhara*, *Trutiya*, *Chathurthi*, *Panchami* and *Shasti*. *Sushruta* mentioned the measurement of seven *Tvacha* layer from 1/18 *Vrihi* to 2 *Vrihi* and also stated that each layer is location of specific disease, in *Avabhasini- Sidhma*, *Padmakantaka*. In *Lohita - Tilakalaka*, *Vyanga*, *Nyachha*, In *Shweta - Charmaaadala*, *Mashaka*, *Ajagallika*, In *Tamra - Killas*, *Kushta*, In *Vedini - Kushta*, *Visarpa*, In *Rohini - Gandamala*, *Apache*, *Shlipad*, *Arbud*, In *Mamsadhara - bhagandhara*, *Arsha*, *Vidradhi*. *Sweda* is one of the trim alas which maintains luster and turgidity of skin. *Sneha* of *Tvacha* (moisture and luster) is *Mala* of *Majja dhatu* as described by *Charak* in *Grahnidoshachikitsa adhyay*. *Charaka* has referred that the person of *Kaphapradana prakriti* is attractive, which indicate that *Kapha* is mainly responsible for luster and texture of skin. In this way all the three *Doshas* have impact on skin. *Tvaka* is a seat of *Rasa Dhatu*. *Rasa Dhatu* plays an important role in the formation of colour and complexion of skin. It good explained by the *Tvakasara purusha* is *Snigdha*, *Shlakshana*, *Komal*, *Prasanna*, *Sukshama* and *Prabhayukta*. *Charaka* has said that *Sudhha Rakta* as a responsible factor for *Sharira Bala*, *Varna*, *Sukha* and *Ayu*. *Charaka* mentioned skin as *Updhatu* of *Maansa* or skin nourishes from *Maansa dhatu*. Also the skin is considered as *Moolsthana* (prime organ) of *Maansvaha* *Srotasa*. *Tvacha*, though *Panchbhautic*, has *Pruthvi Mahabhutadhikya*. *Tvacha* is the *indriya Adhithana* of *Sparshanendriya* which has *Vayu Mahabhutadhikya*. It means *Sthool tvacha* has *Pruthvi Mahabhutadhikya*. Demand of *Raktamokasha* is increased day by day from physicians all over the world. The clinician who knows all about the *Raktamokshan* and their method of application is successful in treating the disease. Various *Tvachavikar* are *Rakta pradoshaj* and *Tridosha prakopaj* and *Chirkari vyadhi*. *Rakta-mokshana* gives best effect in various *Tvachavikar* by expelling the morbid, vitiated *Dosha* and *Dhatu*.^[14-17]

CONCLUSION

Rakthamokshana is ponder as *Ardha chikitsa* and due to *Ashraya ashrayi bhava*, it acts on *Pitta dosha* too. It is

used on site of particular "*Twacha-vikar*", layers of skin nomenclature only in Ayurveda. By *Rakthamokshana*, *Srotoshodhana* is achieved which further helps in abatement of *Tvachavikar*. Various *Tvachavikar* are *Rakta pradoshaj* and *Tridosha prakopaj* and *Chirkari vyadhi*. *Raktamokshana* gives best effect in various *Tvachavikar* by expelling the morbid, vitiated *Dosha* and *Dhatu*. But the effect of therapy is not only by expelling the vitiated blood but *Raktamokashan* also emits some enzymes in the wound. So *Raktamokashna* has also provided normalization and improvement of capillary as well as collateral blood circulation, expressed anti-inflammatory effect, Immune stimulation and Immune-modulating effect and early wound healing effect. All of this reaction may be effect of such salivary enzymes like *Hirudin* anticoagulant effect with diuretics, antibiotic action, *Colin* prevent blood coagulation, *Eglin*, *antitrypsin* *hyaluronidase*, *antithrombin* and *antichymotrypsin* etc. *Raktamokashan* are the perfect solution for many skin diseases. Demand of *Raktamokasha* is increased day by day from physicians all over the world. The clinician who knows all about the *Raktamokshan* and their method of application is successful in treating the disease. So *Raktamokshan* is one of the important *Panckarma* treatments to cure various type of *Tvacha vikar*.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla & Prof. Ravi Dutta Tripathi, *Charak samhita sutrasthana*, *Nibandha samgraha* and *naya chandrika* by *Dalhana Varanasi*: *Chaukambha Surbharti* publication, 2002; page. no. 75.
2. Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla & Prof. Ravi Dutta Tripathi, *Charak samhita sutrasthana*, *Varanasi*: *Chaukambha Surbharti* publication; *vidyothini commentary*, 2002; page no. 45.
3. Acharya Brahmanand Tripathi, *Ashtang Hriday sutrasthana-vidyothini commentary*, *Delhi*: *Chaukambha Surbharti* publication; *vidyothini commentary*, 2002; page no. 277.
4. Acharya Dr. Anantram Sharma, *Sushrut samhita sharer stahna*, *Varanasi*: *Chaukambha Surbharti* publication; *vidyothini commentary*, 2002; page no. 761.
5. Dr. G. Shrinivas acharya, *Panchakarma illustrated*. *Chukhmbha Sanskrit Prakahan*, 2015; Page no. 237.
6. Excellence of Ayurvedic Healing and Ayurvedic Treatment by (cited April3, 2015). Available www.dronicakrishan.com/why-ayurvedic-Treatment-are-the-best/
7. Sushrut, *Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary*, *Varanasi*: *Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan*, Volume 1, *Sutra Sthan*, Chapter 13, Edition: Reprint, 2015; page no. 57.
8. Sushrut, *Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary*, *Varanasi*: *Chaukhambha Sanskrita*

- Sansthan, Volume 1, Sutra Sthan, Chapter 13, Edition: Reprint 2015; page no. 57.
9. Sushrut, Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan, Volume 1, Sutra Sthan, chapter 13, Edition: Reprint, 2015; page no. 59.
 10. Sushrut, Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan, Volume 1, Sutra Sthan, Chapter 14, Edition: Reprint, 2015; page no. 56.
 11. Sushrut, Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan, Volume 1, Shareer Sthan, Chapter 8, Edition: Reprint, 2015; page no. 88.
 12. Sushrut, Ambika Dutta Shastri, Sushrut Samahita with Elaborated Ayurveda Tatva Sandipika Hindi Commentary, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan, Volume 1, Sutra Sthan, Chapter 14, Edition: Reprint, 2015; page no. 79.
 13. Dr. G. Shrinivas acharya, Panchakarma illustrated. Chukhmbha Sanskrit Prakahana, 2015; Page no. 237.
 14. Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla & Prof. Ravi Dutta Tripathi, Charak samhita sutrasthana, Nibandha samgraha and naya chandrika by Dalhana Varanasi: Chaukambha Surbharti publication, 2002; page. no. 75.
 15. Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla & Prof. Ravi Dutta Tripathi, Charak samhita sutrasthana, Varanasi: Chaukambha Surbharti publication; vidyothini commentary, 2002; page no. 45.
 16. Acharya Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang Hriday sutrasthana-vidyothini commentary, Delhi: Chaukambha Surbharti publication; vidyothini commentary, 2002; page no. 277.
 17. Shukla vidyadhar, tripathi ravi dutt, editors. charak samhita of Agnivesha Delhi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit pratisthan, 2002; page. no364.